

Code		Description	Participants who mentioned	Examples
Information management	Prioritization based on tasks	The super bot presents the most important bots comments based on the task implemented by the developer.	P2, P6, P7, P8, P10, P13, P22, P24, P27	"it would also be able to sort of filter out what's useful and what's not useful based on that task the developer is actually working on." [P10]
	Prioritization based on issues	The super bot should display the critical bot notifications, including errors and failures.	P2, P13, P15, P18, P21, P23, P24	"if any critical problem happens, then I would like to be notified with a specific bot report, I would receive a critical notification." [P21]
	Summarization of bot comments	The super bot summaries bots outputs into a single comment on a pull request.	P4, P6, P7, P10, P18, P24, P26, P28, P29, P31, P32	"It is difficult to summarize, right? Because, although the message is created by a bot, it's supposedly based on a template." [P31] "Give me a context report or summary. I expect the Super bot to be just one particular comment with some points. Just one comment with everything as a conscious report." [p26]
	Categorization of bot comments	The super bot groups the bot comments based on their types (e.g., testing, security).	P9, P23, P27, P30, P31	" I would categorize the events by type, if it's everything related to coveralls, everything related to license, everything related to vulnerabilities updated versions that we can have a clear vision, because the developer will know what is the priority of each task and wil know if it needs to look at it or not." [P27]
	Aggregating bot comments	The super bot merges bots outputs into a single comment on a pull request.	P4, P8, P10, P14, P15, P16, P24, P30, P32	I mean, the simplest way is just to put them together, but I don't think it's that easy." [P4]
	Keep the most recent information	The super bot creates a comment and keeps updating the comment with new information from other bots to avoid inflating the pull requests and issues with many comments.	P2, P7, P8, P16, P23, P25, P27	"the super bot just creates one comment and keeps updating it for example." [P16]
	Interacting with users through natural language	The super bot would provide an interface for communicating with developers in order to understand their requests and answer their questions.	P2, P5, P18, P26	"So in that case, I expect the super bot to be actively involved in the discussion, and not some automated script, which just executes one out of the pre-listed responses." [P26]
	Internationalization	The super bot supports different languages (e.g. German)	P1, P22	"The language itself could be English or maybe the language you set up on GitHub if there is a feature to say "I'm from Germany. So I want the UI to be in German" than the super bot could use this information and provide German messages." [P1]
Platform support	Separating bot comments	The GitHub should display bot comments in another panel/session of the pull request interface.	P2, P5, P7, P16, P17, P19, P25, P26, P27, P31, P32	"So I would create another thread for automatic messages. In the pull request, the interface would be able to split the conversation. It would eliminate the problem of typing in the middle of the conversation." [P17] "developers do not like bots to come in the middle of their conversations. So, bots having their own space or their own channel would be the best." [P32]

	Bots configuration dashboard	The GitHub would provide a way to access a dashboard that is customizable to the developers needs that could depend on the developers role in the project.	P3, P7, P11, P17	"you end up with tons of repositories and if bots are working on it, you need some overview picture of it." [P3]
Newcomers' assistance	Welcoming message	The super bot welcomes the newcomers by posting a comment, for example "Hi, this is your first contribution. Welcome abroad!"	P2, P10, P15, P20, P21, P23, P24, P25	"as soon as possible you will receive the message "Hi, welcome! I just saw this is your first contribution. Are you aware of the rules of this repository?" or "the rules of this community". [P2] "to let them know that they're welcome into this community." [P10]
	Explaining rules, instructions, and requirements	The super bot should guide the newcomers and inform them about the projects rules and the requirement to approve the PR.	P2, P6, P13, P14, P15, P20, P21, P23	"[the newcomer] do not understand the rules yet and [the newcomer] don't understand which rules are important." [P13] "the super bot would do an excellent job for a newcomer by explaining why these rules exist." [P13]
	Provide information interactively	The super bot provides information one at a time and communicates with users.	P5, P8, P9, P20, P21	"super bot could do what chatbots do today: guide the new contributor. So, kind of step by step to guide the newcomer" [P5]
	Newcomers pull request notification	The super bot notifies expert developers about a newcomer's contribution.	P1, P6, P8	"[...] and maybe also ping a developer to look at it because it's a new contributor." [P1]
Notification management	Schedule bot notifications	The super bot would not notify developers on the predefined times they have configured the bot to not interrupt them with notifications (e.g. "do not disturb" mode).	P2, P5, P7, P8, P12, P25, P27	"I was wondering if we could try to create some kind of interface for the level of availability of the interruptions." [P2]
	Do not notify maintainers until pull request is ready to review	The super bot would notify the developers only when the predefined rules were reached.	P16, P27	"I want to be notified about new pull requests after all my tests have passed. And after the bots commented, and if everything is green, then I want to be notified" [P16]
	Notify developers in their idle times	The super bot would not interrupt the developers during critical tasks. Also, the super bot has the ability to learn with the developers' schedule and adapt to them.	P1, P5, P7, P10, P24, P26, P27	"You could fix this issue by not notifying the developer if you're aware that he is currently working. That's also what other humans would not do." [P1]
	Notify through pre-specified channel	The super bot should send the notifications wherever the developer wants to receive the notification (e.g. email, GitHub notifications, ...)	P1, P4, P5, P8, P10, P15, P23, P24	"I think, since it's a super bot, and some of the complaints are that they didn't like information overload, it would be useful for it to make notifications in whatever way the user prefers." [P10]
	Notifying interested developers	The super bot notifies the developers who are interested in monitoring activities related to a particular Repo/issue/PR.	P2, P16, P25, P27, P28	" if I'm just a contributor, hey, I want to know that notification about that contribution that I made to the project. But as a maintainer, I don't need to know, I don't need to be reminded again, about every contribution that happened when I release a new version of my project" [P25]

Spam and failures management	Prevent repetitive bot activities	The super bot would detect bots that are generating repetitive outcomes and prevent them from acting on pull requests and issues, in order to avoid duplicate messages and spam.	P1, P6, P10, P11, P24, P25, P26, P27	""If it has the ability to control which bots comment often, then of course, it would be easy to say "no, you only have this one comment and I see that your next comment is exactly the same. I won't let you comment." That would be maybe the easiest solution. I don't know if ... Okay, assuming that the super bot is super intelligent and really knows that the second comment is a bug. Although it is totally different, it doesn't make sense." [P1]
	Bugs report	The super bot would be able to create an issue in the smaller bots repository to report bugs with them.	P1, P10	""Maybe the super bot could create a pull request or issue in the other bots repository and tell them "Hey, look here, I found the bot bugs". Maybe that was something that's really cool and really futuristic. If super bot creates the issues on other repositories." [P1]
	Spam messages notification	The super bot would notify developers of repetitive bot messages that might be considered spam.	P1, P10, P25, P26	""So there should be some sort of feedback for developers whenever they receive a bot notification or so this wouldn't actually be coming from super bot." [P10]